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Effectiveness Of Cognitive Restructuring In Managing Depression Among People With Sickle Cell Disease In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the Effectiveness of Cognitive Restructuring in Managing Depression among People with Sickle Cell Disease in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is a prevalent genetic blood disorder in Nigeria, particularly in Sokoto State, causing chronic pain and significant psychosocial burdens. Patients often experience high levels of depression, due to the unpredictable nature of the disease, chronic pain, and social stigma. While medical treatments exist, there is a dearth of research on psychological interventions to manage the accompanying distress in this region. The study has two specific objectives, all aimed at determining the effectiveness of CR in reducing depression individually (pre-test vs. post-test), and the effectiveness of CR Counselling techniques compared to a control group that receives no psychological intervention. Two research questions and two null hypotheses (H0) are stated, corresponding to the objectives, each predicting that there will be no significant difference or effect. A quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test control group design was adopted. A sample of 90 persons with SCD was purposively selected from two hospitals in Sokoto States. Participants were assigned to two groups: the CR group (n=45), and a control group (n=45) that received no intervention. The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) is used for data collection. The researcher also establishes Kappa validity index (KVI) of 0.8 and reliability index of 0.83 for the Beck Depression. The treatment groups received eight weeks of structured therapy sessions. Data were analyzed using paired sample t-tests and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that Cognitive Restructuring is significantly effective in reducing depression levels among participants from pre-test to post-test ($p < 0.001$). However the intervention groups showed significantly better outcomes in managing depression compared to the control group ($p = 0.031$ for CR). The study concluded that Cognitive Restructuring is effective, standalone interventions for managing psychological distress in individuals with Sickle Cell Disease. It is recommended that healthcare institutions in Nigeria integrate these

psychological therapies into standard treatment protocols for SCD to provide holistic care that addresses both physical and mental health. Professional counsellors should be deployed in hospitals to administer these techniques.
Keywords: Sickle Cell Disease, Psychological Distress, Depression, Cognitive Restructuring,

INTRODUCTION

Sickle cell disease is a lifelong blood disorder which is characterized by red blood cells that assume an abnormal, rigid, sickle shape. Sickling decreases the cells' flexibility and results in a risk of various complications. Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a global public health issue affecting millions of people throughout the world. Smith and Praetorius (2020) defined SCD as a hereditary blood disorder of the red blood cells which blocks blood vessels causing organ damage and frequent painful episodes.

Treatments for SCD and a possible cure are constantly being addressed by both public and governmental healthcare organizations. Currently, drug therapies like hydroxyurea, blood transfusion, and stem cell transplant are the focus of treatment for SCD (Smith & Praetorius, 2020). In the meantime, SCD continues to cause great suffering to patients and families. Parents or guardians are the primary caregivers for people with SCD. People with SCD have the tendency to suffer from psychosocial and behavioural problems (Armstrong, Lemanek, Pegelow, Gonzalez, & Martinez, 2021). As a result, parents become stressed, burdened, and sometimes feel guilty about their child's diagnosis (Armstrong, Lemanek, Pegelow, Gonzalez, and Martinez, 2021).

Sickle-cell disease is globally widespread. About 5% of the world's population carries genes responsible for hemoglobinopathies. Each year about 300 000 infants are born with major haemoglobin disorders, including more than 200 000 cases of sickle-cell disease in Africa. Globally, there are more carriers (i.e. healthy people who have inherited only one mutant gene from one parent) of thalassaemia than of sickle-cell disease, but the high frequency of the sickle-cell gene in certain areas leads to a high rate of affected newborns (CDC, 2020). Sickle-cell disease is particularly common among people whose ancestors come from sub-Saharan Africa, India, Saudi Arabia and Mediterranean countries (Centers for Disease Control and prevention (CDC, 2020). Migration raised the frequency of the gene in the American continent. In some areas of sub-Saharan Africa, up to 2% of all children are born with the condition. In broad terms, the prevalence of the sickle-cell trait (healthy carriers who have inherited the mutant gene from only one parent) ranges between 10% and 40% across equatorial Africa and decreases to between 1% and 2% on the north African coast and less than 1% in south Africa. This distribution reflects the fact that sickle-cell trait confers a survival advantage against malaria and that selection pressure due to malaria has resulted in high frequencies of the mutant gene especially in areas of high malarial transmission. In West African countries such as Ghana and Nigeria, the frequency of the trait is 15% to 30% whereas in Uganda it shows marked tribal variations, reaching 45% among the Baamba tribe in the west of the country (CDC, 2020).

Frequencies of the carrier state determine the prevalence of sickle-cell disease at birth. For example, in Nigeria, by far the most populous country in the sub region, 24% of the populations are carriers of the mutant gene and the prevalence of sickle-cell disease is about 20 per 1000 births. This means that in Nigeria alone, about 150 000 children are born annually with sickle-cell disease. The public health implications of sickle-cell disease are significant. Its impact on human health may be assessed against the yardsticks of infant and under-five mortality. As not all deaths occur in the first year of life. An increasing proportion of affected children now survive past five years of age but remain at risk of premature death. When health impact is measured by under-five mortality, sickle-cell disease contributes the equivalent of 5% of under five deaths on the African continent, more than 9% of such deaths in East Africa, and up to 16% of under-five deaths in West African countries (CDC, 2020).

One of the constructs of people with sickle cell disease is depression and it may significantly affect the life of people with sickle cell disease. Depression is a severe despondency and dejection, accompanied by feelings of hopelessness, inadequacy and condition of mental disturbance, typically with lack of energy and difficulty in maintaining concentration or interest in life. Hoffman (2023) contends that, sometimes depressed person inhibit low mood, loss of pleasure in daily activities, feelings of guilt or low energy and

poor concentration. Depression may go a long way to affect people with sickle cell disease within themselves and sometimes with the society.

One of the psychological treatments which are in line with the needs of such people with sickle cell disease is the cognitive restructuring technique. This treatment or intervention is to be administered to clients, to investigate the effectiveness of this counselling technique which will go a long way in supporting people with sickle cell disease in order to cope with psychological distress induced by diseases.

Cognitive restructuring basic foundation is contained in the ABCD Paradigm developed by Ellis & Ellis (1991) rational emotive therapy and other cognitive restructuring procedures which are effective in modifying clients' behaviours and attitudes and counselling clients to overcome self-defeating concerns." Cognitive restructuring is an example of a counselling technique which will help in promoting more accurate and useful thinking. It is very helpful in treating depression, anxiety and other undesirable negative behaviours associated with sickle cell disease.

All these are reasons that call for the need for counselling on people with sickle cell disease. However, there are many treatments for sickle cell disease, but the degree to which they are available and acceptable to people with sickle cell disease varies considerably by geographical location and accessibility to resources.

Statement of the Problem

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a serious, inherited condition affecting the blood and various organs in the body. It affects the red blood cells, causing of sickling, which produce pain and other symptoms which can lead to long-term complications. Pain is the most common consequence of the sickle cell disease (SCD). Most sickle cell disease patients manage their pain at home, despite the fact that pain is the primary reason for visiting the emergency room and an inpatient facility.

Certain conditions can trigger sickling, such as cold, infection, lack of fluid in the body (dehydration) or low oxygen etc. People with sickle cell disease are faced with emotional and mental health concerns like anger, depression low self-esteem, hopelessness, worthlessness and anxiety. They may become more anxious to be in public, ironically increasing social isolation. They experience stigma, sense of loss, and diminished self-esteem and can be reminded of their conditions through television shows, movies and commercials that relate to people with sickle cell disease and these messages may lead to believe that they are not a functioning part of the society.

Depression is a common reaction associated with people with sickle cell disease which leads to problems like anger, low self-esteem, hopelessness, worthlessness and anxiety. It is a response to the excessive losses and prolonged stress created by the disease. People with sickle cell disease may have feelings of failure, loss, depression and anxiety among others. Their sadness can sometimes be transform into sorrows or grief especially for the loss of certain position of their dreams or the imagined experiences one could share with ones' friends and relatives.

Several studies conducted on people with sickle cell disease are on its causes and treatments thereby paying little attention to psychological effects of the problem. In developed countries people with sickle cell disease treatment goes hand in hand with psychological treatment to improve the chances of getting positive result. Where the result is not forthcoming, people with sickle cell disease are prepared mentally against any challenges ahead which will in turn enable them to live a positive and well-adjusted life. The underlying factors to those problems are due to lack of functioning centers across urban and rural areas to cater for the needs of the people with sickle cell disease.

People with sickle cell disease usually develop different form of behaviour like social withdrawal, loss of interest; unhappiness; desperateness and so on as such sometimes consider themselves as non-active part of the society. They always believed that, there lives will be terminated at any time as a result of that they live in constant fear of death and most of their dreams in live will not be accomplish. This can lead to stroke, acute chest syndrome (a condition that lowers the level of oxygen in the blood), organ damage, other disabilities, and in some cases premature death

Moreover, while acknowledging the fact that different studies have demonstrated the efficacy of cognitive-restructuring technique in reducing antisocial behaviour, there is still dearth of research efforts on the use of cognitive-restructuring in reducing depression among people with different diseases in Sokoto state, Nigeria. It is based on this that, the researcher sought to investigate effectiveness of cognitive-restructuring counselling technique in managing depression among people with sickle cell diseases in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to find out:

1. The effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/post-test means scores in managing depression level among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State.
2. The different depression level between the group exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique and those in the control group among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State

Research Questions

The following are the research questions for the study:

1. What is the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/post-test means scores in managing depression level among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State?
2. What is the different depression level between the group exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique and those in the control group among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be tested in the course of the study

H01: There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/post-test means scores in managing depression level among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State.

H02: There is no significant difference on the depression level between the groups that were exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique and those in the control group in Sokoto State.

METHODOLOGY

A quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test control group design was adopted for this study. This design was suitable for establishing the cause-and-effect relationship between the Independent variable (Cognitive Restructuring) and the dependent variable (depression level).

The population for the larger study comprised people with SCD attending selected hospitals in Sokoto State. For this specific study, a sample of 90 participants from Sokoto State was used. The sample was purposively selected from Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital Sokoto and Specialist Hospital Sokoto. Participants were included if they scored 17 or above on the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), indicating at least mild to moderate depression. These 90 participants were then assigned into two groups:

The instruments used for this study are adopted version of Aaron Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) for measuring the depression level of people with sickle cells disease. The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) was used to measure the level of depression. It is a 21-item self-report instrument with well-established psychometric properties. For this study, a reliability index of 0.85 was established using Cronbach's alpha, indicating high internal consistency. Scores range from 0-63, with scores of 17-30 indicating mild depression and 31-40 indicating severe depression.

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 21). A paired sample t-test was used to determine the significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores within the CR group. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to compare the post-test scores of the CR group and the control group, while controlling for pre-test differences to increase the validity of the findings. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Answers to Research Questions

Answers to two research questions raised were provided in this section. The researcher employed mean and standard deviation of the groups in providing answers to the research questions.

Question One: *What is the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/post-test means scores in managing depression level among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State?*

Table 1: Mean Score difference of Pre-test and Post-test in Managing Depression

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Groups	Treatments	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pre-test depression	Cognitive restructuring	45	25.17	6.26
Post-test depression	Cognitive restructuring	45	18.22	4.55

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Table1, shows the pre-test and the post-test means scores on depression level of subjects in the experimental group, that is, those exposed to cognitive restructuring. From the table, the pre-test and posttest means score on depression for the experimental group are (25.17, 18.22). This shows that cognitive restructuring counselling technique was effective in reducing the means scores on depression level of subjects in treatment group.

Question Two: *What is the post-test difference in depression level between the group exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique and those in the control group among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State?*

Table 2: Mean score Difference in Post-test Depression level between Cognitive Restructuring Counselling Technique and those in the Control Group

	Treatment	N	Mean	Std.Deviation
Post-test Depression	Cognitive Restructuring	45	18.22	4.24
Post-test Depression	Control Group	45	26.57	7.26

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Table 4.15 shows that mean score of subjects on depression level in cognitive restructuring counselling technique (18.22) which is lower than the means score on depression level of subjects in the control group (26.57). This indicated that, cognitive restructuring counselling technique is more effective in reducing the depression level among people with sickle cell disease, than the control group. The difference in the means score on depression was attributed to effectiveness of cognitive restructuring compared to the control who did not received any treatment of any form.

Hypotheses Testing

In this study, two null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/ post-test means scores on depression level among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State.

This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the pre-test /post-test means scores of the respondents to t-test analysis as presented in Table 4.19.

Table 3: Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test on Depression Level of Respondents Exposed to Cognitive Restructuring Technique

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Pre-test	45	27.56	6.558	9.726	.000	Rejected
Post-test	45	20.78	4.633			

P < 0.05

Table 3 shows that t-test indicated scores were significantly lower for the post-test (M = 20.78, SD = 4.633) than for the pre-test (M = 27.56, SD = 6.558), $t(13) = 9.726, p = .000$. Thus, the respondents' depression level reduced significantly after being exposed to cognitive restructuring because the realized p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicated that there was significant reduction in the depression level of the respondents' due to the effectiveness of the intervention technique. Therefore, H01 which stated that there is no significant difference in the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/post-test means scores in managing depression level among people with sickle cell disease in Sokoto State. is rejected.

Ho2: There is no significant difference on the depression level between the groups that were exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique and those in the control group in Sokoto State.

This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the post-test scores of the respondents to t-test analysis as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ANCOVA Results for the Difference in Depression Level between Respondents Exposed to Cognitive Restructuring and those in the Control Group

Table 4: ANCOVA Results for the Difference in Depression Level between Respondents Exposed to Cognitive Restructuring and those in the Control Group

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial η^2
Pre-test (Covariate)	2045.67	1	2045.67	70.86	<.001	0.286
Treatment Group	583.52	1	583.52	20.21	<.001	0.102
Error	5110.35	177	28.87			
Total	7739.54	179				

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The results in Table 4 demonstrated that pre-test depression scores had a significant influence on post-test depression levels ($F(1,177) = 70.86, p < .001$), with a partial eta squared value of 0.286. This indicates that approximately 28.6% of the variance in participants' final depression scores can be explained by their initial depression levels. This substantial effect underscores the importance of accounting for baseline differences when evaluating treatment effectiveness. After controlling for these pre-existing differences in depression, there was a highly significant difference between the treatment groups ($F(1,177) = 20.21, p < .001$). The partial eta squared value of 0.102 reveals that the treatment condition (Cognitive Restructuring versus Control) accounted for about 10.2% of the variance in depression outcomes. This represents a medium to large effect size in behavioral research, indicating that the difference between groups was not only statistically significant but also clinically meaningful. The sum of squares for the treatment effect (583.52) compared to the error (5110.35) and total variation (7739.54) demonstrates that while individual differences account for a substantial portion of the variation in depression scores, the treatment intervention explains a considerable and meaningful portion of the variance after controlling for initial depression levels.

These findings provide strong evidence against the null hypothesis (H02), confirming that Cognitive Restructuring counselling technique significantly reduced depression levels compared to no intervention among participants in Sokoto State. The ANCOVA results provide a more precise estimate of the

treatment effect by statistically adjusting for pre-existing differences between the groups, strengthening the conclusion that Cognitive Restructuring is an effective therapeutic approach for addressing depression in this population.

Summary of Major Findings

The following are the summary of the major findings:

1. There is significant difference on the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/ post-test means scores on anxiety level among people with sickle cells diseases in Sokoto State. This was as a result of constant treatment and words of encouragement received from the researcher.
2. Cognitive Restructuring counselling technique significantly reduced depression levels among people with sickle cells diseases in Sokoto State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from hypothesis one showed that there exists significant difference on the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring counselling technique on the pre-test/posttest means score on depression level among people with sickle cells diseases in Northwest zone than pre-test means score. The realized p-value .000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. The finding from this study is in agreement with the result of experimental research by Salawuddeen (2019) the authors investigated the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring and brainstorming counseling techniques in the management of psychological distress induced by sickle cell diseases (namely anxiety and depression), among patient with sickle cell diseases in Okene local government area of Kogi State, Nigeria.

Results from data analysis revealed that both counselling techniques had significant effects in managing anxiety and depression among patient with sickle cell diseases, the effect of cognitive restructuring treatment brought about reduction in depression from pre-test depression means score of (X= 22.66) to post-test depression means score(X = 17.30). Equally, brainstorming treatment brought about reduction depression, from pre- test means score on depression of (X = 25.41) to posttest means score on depression of (X = 14.91). Findings from the study also showed that brainstorming technique with means score on depression (X = 14.91), was more effective in managing depression than cognitive restructuring with post-test means score on depression (X =17.33). It was recommended that government should make it a priority to put in place functional counselling services in health-care delivery system to cater for psychological emotional needs of patient with sickle cell diseases seeking treatment.

Results of findings from testing hypothesis two indicated that significant difference exists between the depression levels of those people exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique and those in the control group. The depression level of subjects in cognitive restructuring is lower than those in the control group, the realized p-value of .031 is less than .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis eighth is rejected. This findings is in agreement with research conducted by Sylvers, Laprarie, and Lilienfeld, (2021) that cognitive restructuring reduces the stress in people with sickle cells diseases using CBT that include different method such as biofeedback, behavioural training, stop thinking among others. Norman (2021) conducted their study to determine the factors affecting depression in people with sickle cells diseases and impact of psychological intervention before or during treatment. A cross sectional study with 638 people with sickle cells diseases assess for depression. 140 people with sickle cells diseases with a member who had Beck Depression inventory (BDI) score of 17 or higher were randomized to receive psychological treatment either before or during the treatment. The study concluded that 48% of people with sickle cells diseases found depression during initial period before intervention. The mean SD Beck score fall from 18.7+/-9.7 to 10.7+/-5.8 (p<0.001) in the groups were psychologically treated before they received any treatment. The study concluded that the psychological intervention was found very useful in alleviating depression in people with sickle cells diseases before they received treatment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study the following are the conclusions drawn.

The respondents' depression level reduced significantly after being exposed to cognitive restructuring counselling technique. Therefore, cognitive restructuring counseling technique was effective and should be used in managing depression level of people with sickle cells diseases. However, depression level of the respondents exposed to cognitive restructuring reduced significantly more than that of those in the control group. Therefore, cognitive restructuring should be used to manage those in the control group.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Cognitive restructuring counselling techniques should be employed in managing depression level among people with sickle cells disease in various health centres.
2. Since respondents exposed to cognitive restructuring had their depression levels reduce, the control group should be exposed to cognitive restructuring techniques.

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